

TRACER STUDIES OF DOCTOR OF EDUCATION MAJOR IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT GRADUATES OF BATANGAS STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This tracer study primarily determined the employability and performance of the of CTE EdD-EM graduates in the inclusive AY 2015-2016- AY 2018-2019 with the end view of proposing a curriculum enhancement plan in order to produce globally competitive graduates. It also determined the respondents' job placement profile, extent of the program's contribution to their personal and professional growth and their work performance. The descriptive method of research was applied in the study using questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. The participants of the study were the EdD-EM graduates of Batangas State University. Results revealed that majority of the graduates from EdD-EM are in the age bracket of 41-50, female, married, other course, MAED-EM graduates, LET passers, permanently employed in public institution, took up their advance study for professional development, work as Teachers with present position of Principal IV, have been employed for more than 20 years and above, and members of PAGE. The EdD-EM programs contributed to graduates' personal and professional growth. The curriculum enhancement plan may produce highly trained and globally competitive graduates. They assessed that doctorate program contributed to their personal and professional growth to great extent. The employers strongly agreed that they have shown critical thinking skills and work ethics in performing their job. It was recommended that the prepared curriculum enhancement activities may be used for the different courses to attain higher level of competencies of graduates.

Keywords: tracer study, Ed EM, curriculum enhancement plan, employability and performance